

Blueprint for a Salmon Knowledge Portal

Meeting Report

1. Table of Contents

1. Table of Contents.....	2
2. Executive Summary.....	3
3. Introduction.....	5
4. Background and Previous Efforts.....	7
5. Envisioning an Ecosystem of Salmon Knowledge Portals.....	8
Barriers and Challenges.....	9
Demonstration Portals.....	13
AYK Chinook App.....	14
DataONE Portal on Salmon Knowledge.....	16
University of Texas El Paso (UTEP) / Nuna Technologies Salmon Map App.....	18
Designing a Portfolio of Salmon Knowledge Applications.....	19
Portal Design and Features.....	21
Knowledge Modeling.....	24
Salmon Data Access.....	26
6. Synthesis, Funding Opportunities, and Collaboration.....	28
7. Acknowledgements.....	30
8. References.....	30
Appendix I: Portals and Resources.....	32
Appendix II: Participants.....	35
Participant Affiliations.....	37
Appendix III: Workshop Agenda.....	40
Appendix IV: Lightning Talks.....	40
References for Graphics and Photos.....	43

Citation:

Maggie Klope, Emily Lescak, Matthew B. Jones, Hajo Eicken, William Manley, Craig Tweedie, Irene D. Alabia, Tom Bird, Hekia Bodwitch, Courtney Carothers, Bruno Carturan, Curry Cunningham, Brandi R. Cron, Graeme Diack, Kelly Drummond, Lara Erikson, Thomas Farrugia, Allison Gaylord, Yuki Iino, Brett Johnson, Delores Larson, Jeff Libby, Andrew Magel, An Nguyen, Jamie O'Connor, Gottfried Pestal, Ava Peters, Pete Rand, Mark Saunders, Erik Schoen, Tobias Schwoerer, Tommy Sheridan, Jim Simon, Kelsey Stanbro, Nels Ure, Christine Waigl, and Harmony Wayner. Blueprint for a Salmon Knowledge Portal. 10.5281/zenodo.20347502.

2. Executive Summary

Wild salmon populations across the Pacific and Atlantic face mounting pressures, with sustained declines threatening the cultural, subsistence, commercial and ecological frameworks that rely upon them. Responding effectively requires timely access to a range of information related not only to salmon abundance and life history but also environmental variation, yet such data remains fragmented across agencies, organizations, and countries, with inconsistent standards and limited discoverability.

We convened a hybrid workshop, *Blueprint of a Salmon Knowledge Portal*, in Anchorage, Alaska (November 12-14, 2025) to identify key barriers to data sharing and harmonization, including inconsistent metadata standards, fragmented data systems, limited institutional and community capacity, and inadequate long-term funding. We also discussed tangible next steps for moving forward with data harmonization efforts.

A central conclusion of the workshop was that a single all-purpose salmon portal was not sufficient to meet the diverse needs of data users including community members, researchers, policymakers and managers. Instead, the workshop produced a vision for a portfolio of interconnected applications tailored to specific use cases and based on a foundation of accessible salmon data systems built with open standards. Four conceptual applications were envisioned through a group design session, and despite their differences in focus, common themes included a user-first design approach, the transparency and traceability of data sources, and the support for Indigenous and local knowledge.

The workshop produced several recommendations for moving this work forward. Participants expressed a strong interest in continued collaboration through in-person sessions at established meetings. Additionally, future work could be connected with established organizational frameworks, such as the Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) in the United States, the Research Data Alliance (RDA), Earth Science Information Partners (ESIP), and the International Polar Year.

Participants pointed to emerging technologies, such as advances in artificial intelligence, machine learning, and large language models, as promising tools to enable data stewards to more efficiently harmonize and synthesize disparate datasets to allow for decision making on shorter timescales. Additionally, agile software development, co-production with Indigenous and fishing communities, and good governance practices are vital for creating a platform that meets user needs, builds trust, and inspires data producers to continue to contribute data and applications, ensuring the platforms' continued relevance for years to come.

This workshop demonstrated that the knowledge, technology, and partnerships necessary for creating these portals are available, and that a coordinated approach to salmon knowledge portals is needed and within reach. Success will require iterative development, beginning with investment in shared metadata and data standards by data holders and sustained funding commitments that outlast individual grant cycles.

3. Introduction

Wild salmon runs have historically been a critical component of food systems and cultures in both the Atlantic and Pacific, but have faced significant threats to sustainability. Wild salmon runs are foundational to cultural, subsistence, commercial, and recreational practices for nations across the North Pacific basin, including the U.S., Canada, Russia and Japan. For many, salmon are a vital component of food security, cultural continuity and community well-being. However, salmon in Alaska and beyond are facing sustained declines and increased interannual variability in some areas that are negatively impacting local fisheries and communities. In the Atlantic, concerted efforts to re-establish historically significant salmon runs in eastern North America and Western Europe have emphasized the need for habitat restoration, elimination of barriers to fish migration, and improved habitat quality, all with the goal of increasing population health.

Responding effectively to the challenges impacting salmon relies on access to historical and current knowledge and data about salmon, their fresh and saltwater environments, the people and economies depending on them, and government and management decisions. A key challenge to accessing information on salmon abundance, productivity, harvest, and environmental conditions is that such data is currently distributed across agencies, databases and organizations in multiple countries and adheres to a variety of data and metadata standards. As a result, critical information can be difficult to discover and use, which can limit the ability of researchers and communities to understand and manage responses to changes in salmon distributions and their habitats.

In response to these challenges, the U.S. National Science Foundation-funded Research Networking Activity for Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs; [University of Alaska Fairbanks, n.d.](#)) organized a hybrid workshop titled *Blueprint of a Salmon Knowledge Portal*, which convened in Anchorage, Alaska, on November 12-14, 2025. The workshop brought together a diverse international group of 54 salmon experts,

including state of Alaska, U.S., Canadian and Japanese federal agency managers and scientists, tribal representatives and members, members of the Alaskan fishing community, academics, and data scientists (see Figure S1) to collaboratively share ideas, opportunities and challenges around accessing and reusing salmon-related data, information, and knowledge. Including participants from multiple countries improved our ability to characterize salmon trends across the Pacific and discuss how we can improve data harmonization efforts on a global scale. The goals of the workshop were to identify challenges related to salmon data access, explore features of existing salmon data portals, support the Sustaining Arctic Observing Network (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing Data Systems (ROADS) Salmon Expert Panel focused on salmon in the Bristol Bay region of Alaska, and generate ideas for salmon knowledge portal design, development, and sustainability. Information from this workshop can inform a process for improving salmon data access and software tools that enhance knowledge production for the various use cases and user groups focused on salmon systems throughout the North Pacific.

Over the course of three days, participants engaged in a range of interactive activities designed to:

- Explore the broader context of the wide range of socio-economic, environmental and biological data that have been collected to understand salmon population

dynamics, distribution and relationships to individuals, communities, regions and governance;

- Review existing salmon-related data portals and their designs, functionalities and gaps;
- Share and explore three test portals developed by workshop organizers and participants;
- Map out potential next steps related to the development of portals designed for specific use cases, potential funding to support data harmonization, portal creation efforts, and socializing the need for standardized approaches to data storage and sharing.

This workshop built off of a RNA CoObs-sponsored workshop in 2024 titled, *'Equitable Information Portal Design for Mobilizing Salmon Knowledge'* ([Klope et al., 2024](#)), which conducted a high-level needs assessment, identified targeted portal users, prioritized potential data to be included, and strategized engagement with data holders.

4. Background and Previous Efforts

This workshop built on a series of prior efforts to identify barriers to salmon data access and mobilization (i.e., the process of making data accessible and usable across data systems) and pathways to meeting those challenges undertaken by multiple organizations (see [Diack et al. 2024](#) and [Appendix I](#)). There is a long history of salmon data access efforts in the Pacific Northwest, including work on the Columbia, Fraser and other major salmon rivers by the Pacific Northwest Aquatic Monitoring Partnership (PNAMP), Fisheries and Oceans Canada (DFO), and the Pacific Salmon Explorer. In Alaska, the Moore Foundation funded the "State of Alaska's Salmon and People Project (SASAP)" which convened over 100 salmon researchers, managers, community and tribal members, and data scientists to synthesize data and information on salmon in Alaska and their importance to community

well-being. The SASAP project compiled, harmonized, and published over 130 integrated datasets ([DataONE, n.d.](#)) from highly distributed sources that spanned multiple decades, some of which provided the first-ever comprehensive integration of Alaskan salmon data spanning 60 years or more. This major data mobilization effort led to new knowledge on many aspects of salmon, including the declining size and age of salmon ([Oke et al., 2020](#)), well-being and salmon systems ([Donkersloot et al., 2020](#)), salmon in changing ocean conditions ([Rand & Ruggerone, 2024](#)), and salmon governance and management as reflected in the public record ([Krupa et al., 2018](#)). While SASAP was highly successful, it concluded in 2018, and since then, an additional eight years of salmon data have been collected that were not incorporated into these integrated data sets, highlighting the need to deeply embed open data principles and practices and sustainability plans in our academic, agency, and tribal salmon initiatives.

During and after SASAP, other initiatives for salmon data access have unfolded, including salmon data efforts by the [Atlantic Salmon Trust](#) ([Diack et al., 2022](#)), the Pacific Salmon Foundation with its [Salmon Data Explorer](#), the Department of Fisheries and Oceans Canada, and the [International Year of the Salmon](#) (IYS) initiative, [Basin-Scale Events and Coastal Impacts \(BECI\)](#), among many others. These and other initiatives led to the formation of an ad-hoc salmon data mobilization group, which morphed into an international [Salmon Research and Monitoring Interest Group](#) organized under the Research Data Alliance. Participants of these groups have been persistently calling for salmon data mobilization and industry and agency support for open data on salmon systems for some years ([Diack et al., 2024](#)).

5. Envisioning an Ecosystem of Salmon Knowledge Portals

With the goal of identifying pathways toward more integrated, accessible, and equitable salmon knowledge infrastructure, participants moved from establishing a shared understanding of the current landscape to collaboratively identify concrete solutions.

Participants delivered a series of lightning talks spanning a wide range of topics including regional overviews of salmon research, salmon knowledge and data stewardship, fisheries and habitat management, and current web applications and partnerships. The presentations underscored the breadth of current work as well as the disjointed nature of salmon data, knowledge, and information across fields. Through a review of three web applications, knowledge modeling, and collaborative design of new application concepts, participants worked towards solutions for removing barriers to salmon information availability and sharing.

Barriers and Challenges

Early in the workshop, participants discussed the question: “What are the major barriers and solutions to realizing data portals that provide shared, international access to integrated, timely salmon data and software tools to enhance decision making?” **The foremost, overarching challenge was identified as the need for salmon data to be open, discoverable, and accessible.** We explored related considerations such as incentives, data sovereignty, and the potential for misuse, particularly where data is taken out of context or applied in ways that undermine Indigenous data governance or influence management decisions without appropriate consultation. Possible pathways forward included a renewed focus on ethically open data policies, as well as demonstrating the value of open data sharing while building awareness and trust with data producers and users.

Another barrier relates to the inconsistent interoperability of salmon data – with solutions ranging from further adoption of metadata standards and vocabularies to

building tools to crosswalk or translate across implementations to improving capacities for automated machine-to-machine data access and exchange. Participants recognized the fragmented and isolated nature of diverse data sources, pointing toward the need for registries or connected systems. Some called for more collaboration, communication, stewardship, and governance. Encompassing all of the challenges was the expressed need for sustained and diversified funding to adequately build capacity among agency, Tribal, and academic partners. For more details on these topics, see Table 1 below.

Table 1. A summary of barriers and challenges to the sharing of salmon data and potential pathways for overcoming these impediments.

Barriers and Challenges	Pathways to Overcome Barriers
Data Access	
Lack of common international policies and procedures and incentives for data holders to share their data openly	Funding to support data stewardship; open data policies from journals and funders (e.g., require data submission along with paper submissions; funding requirement to share data).
	Research data life cycles should be considered as a continual pathway through multiple projects with goals predefined by researchers who are involved.
	Build consensus and vision on goals; write one-pagers to inform policymakers; build awareness across communities.
	Modify or create international data-sharing policies to identify a course of action and expectations, thus showcasing both bottom-up and top-down strategies.
Data sovereignty (Tribes and government agencies)	Ability to manage access, sharing, and ownership over their data that allows for situationally-appropriate confidential data collection and access, while adhering to community values and needs.
Inherent challenge of missing context, misinterpretation (human & AI) and lack of trust	Digestible visualization and establishing reliance on routinely updated data portal products (e.g.,

that the people using the data have good intentions	Windy-type app for in-season data and salmon tracking efforts and Backyard Buoys for wave height).
Proprietary Government Ownership - releasing data in a timely manner	Making high-profile, government-published data usable and demonstrating its utility to encourage more support for open data policies and practice; providing funding and other resources to government agencies to staff these efforts.
Funding	
Need funding to support participation by the organizations that monitor salmon	A grant led by academic researchers that includes funding for the agencies and Tribes that collect the data. Need funding across nations and organizations to build, adopt and maintain an international portal.
Government agency staff capacity limitations - need staff time and upfront development costs to build and maintain a data catalog	Partner with a university. Integrate salmon data lessons and skills into K-12 STEM initiatives, such as Science Olympiad (Junior High School students), and Teaching Through Technology (High School students).
Sustained Funding	Annual federal appropriations through a program such as the Pacific Coastal Salmon Recovery Fund (PCSRF) or other aligned, existing funding program that would contribute to an international repository for Pacific Salmon Data.
Data Interoperability	
Lack of compliance with open standards; barrier to interoperability due to metadata standards differences.	Need publishers and funders to enforce practices. Create an exchange or conversion service that can handle multiple metadata dialects.
How to handle differences in languages, definitions, formats, and ontologies in metadata	Use large language models and machine learning for translation, ingestion/formatting, and transcription to lower barriers.
Need to input data/knowledge in natural language that gets formally structured and translated and is simple to use in a format that is accessible to	Hire artists to translate knowledge, local guides/interpreters of information. Leverage technology (e.g., artificial intelligence and large

diverse users	language models) for metadata translation.
Combining and leveraging datasets	Standardize and communicate between datasets.
Support the inclusion of Indigenous data with western science data	Welcome both qualitative and quantitative data as inputs. Allow for multiple ways of visualizing information, such as story maps.
Disconnected Data Sources	
Fragmented landscape of disconnected salmon data producers; knowing what data are available	Inventory, map, or catalog of salmon data producers, along with a database or registry of salmon-related observing assets (such as weirs, towers, and surveys) along with agencies or organizations responsible for collecting data at those locations.
Isolated data systems across agencies	Each agency publishes a lightweight metadata standard about their holdings.
Governance	
Stewardship at the international level	Create an international organization (funded by data contributors) responsible for harmonizing the salmon data on an international scale.
Governance to engage data holders across the life history of salmon	Create a Data Collaborative across all salmon organizations; e.g., Pacific Northwest Aquatic Monitoring Partnership (PNAMP) uses this approach but has expanded to other countries and Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RMFOs). Utilize Knowledge/Synthesis centres; e.g., Basin-Scale Events and Coastal Impacts (BECI) and PNAMP.
How to use movements like the International Polar Year (IPY), national platforms like IARPC and international platforms like the Research Data Alliance (RDA) to advocate for good data sharing practices	Encourage participation in these processes to raise awareness about why this is important and foster international collaborations to make progress.
Lack of systems to preserve the historic decision-making record, including management decisions and regulatory actions	Invest in archiving governance records (see Krupa et al., 2018 work on Board of Fisheries proposals)
Other	

Lack of awareness of the problem	Educational training and outreach to reach various stakeholders and audiences: e.g., create a Portal relevant to K-16; don't recreate the wheel; look at existing models e.g., (Ch 8. "Promoting Lifelong Ocean Education").
Difficulty identifying a single shared platform that works for all contributors and users	Create a framework that allows for the creation of multiple portals each targeted on specific use-cases.
Lack of understanding of what has prevented success in past efforts	Learning from history; e.g., understanding why Arctic-Yukon-Kuskokwim (AYK) data sharing is ahead of other regions in terms of sharing salmon data; reflecting on issues in previous projects to identify more targeted solutions.

Demonstration Portals

Three salmon information portals were presented to showcase their content and features, and to evaluate the extent to which they address recommendations from our 2024 workshop, including the needs to:

- Create an inventory of salmon counting and observing locations and assets with associated funding support, including an analysis of change over time;

- Design a portal that promotes and respects data equity, data sovereignty, and informed consent;
- Make salmon data more equitably accessible to Tribes, community members, researchers, and decision- and policy-makers.

The portals, described below, promoted discussion about the content, features, interface, usability, and challenges of creating salmon data portals that are integrated, timely, and open.

AYK Chinook App

Erik Schoen (University of Alaska Fairbanks) presented a purpose-built app designed to facilitate data visualization and synthesis for a collaborative research project. The Chinook Salmon Data for the Arctic-Yukon-Kuskokwim (AYK) Region Shiny App (<https://wvo52l-megan0feddern.shinyapps.io/AYKChinook/>) was developed by collaborator Megan Feddern for interactive use at a 2022 workshop focused on drivers of Chinook salmon populations (Feddern et al. 2023). The app allowed workshop participants to rapidly visualize the availability and quality of fisheries and environmental datasets from across the AYK region while designing studies to quantify key drivers and their associations with Chinook salmon populations (Feddern et al. 2024, Shaftel et al. 2026).

This use case highlighted how challenging yet valuable the synthesizing information from different elements of a salmon observation network can be. This work is difficult because data are often sparse or not collected at the same sites on a yearly basis, are managed across multiple agencies and organizations without standardization, and are not made available in machine-readable formats. Additional challenges include funding gaps, equipment lost to extreme weather events, missing fish counts, and uncertainty about funding and filling manager and researcher positions. In this case, data synthesis was greatly facilitated by the Alaska Department of Fish and Game's (ADF&G) prior work in assembling and maintaining a database of salmon data collected by various organizations

in the AYK region ([ADF&G 2026](#)); yet the additional work of building the app made the data more accessible and usable for broad-scale analyses.

Figure 1. Example screenshot of the Shiny App interface, showing Chinook escapement observing assets along the U.S. portion of the Yukon River.

The app used the Arctic-Yukon-Kuskokwim (AYK) region of Alaska as a case study to investigate salmon data availability across locations and time (see Figure 1). The session concluded with a proposal to apply the work to additional regions of Alaska. This would include documenting who manages each project and how it is funded, visualizing patterns and trends, and identifying challenges and opportunities for sustaining Alaska's salmon monitoring systems. The goal is to build a data-driven argument that salmon monitoring projects and teams are essential and worthy of sustained investment. The proposed approach towards a comprehensive assessment of fluctuations and distribution of counting assets in space and time is to review published literature and reports, request data from ADF&G, US Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS), Tribes, and other organizations active in salmon monitoring, and improve mechanisms for monitoring automation. Another aspect of the proposed work includes interviews with researchers, managers, and community members about the reasons for and impacts of the loss of observing assets on management.

DataONE Portal on Salmon Knowledge

This session highlighted the Arctic Data Center's development of a salmon knowledge portal using the DataONE portal framework (<https://search.dataone.org/portals/salmon-portal>) to explore ways of integrating and sharing salmon information. DataONE is a federated network of data repositories that enables users to search across 65+ member repositories. The salmon knowledge portal contains over 2,000 DataONE salmon-related datasets, demonstrating the value of interoperable data systems. In response to recommendations to develop a mockup portal for a single region, the prototype focused on Bristol Bay in Alaska, the focal area of the SAON ROADS Salmon Expert Panel.

Figure 2. Screenshot of a web application in the DataONE Draft Salmon Knowledge Portal. Here, it is plotting Alaska Board of Fisheries Proposals over time, with the color corresponding to different sectors.

The Portal contains a flexible, interactive map-based interface that can display different geospatial datasets individually or as part of a collection. Users can navigate layers, click on features to get more information, and follow links to the original data sources. The integration of interactive tools alongside datasets supports data exploration and interpretation. Examples presented included a Board of Fisheries Proposal Shiny Application, a Story Map for exploring Alaska salmon size and age decline, and a Dashboard on Bristol Bay subsistence use.

University of Texas El Paso (UTEP) / Nuna Technologies Salmon Map App

Craig Tweedie (UTEP) and Allison Gaylord (Nuna Technologies) presented a prototype salmon web mapping application built in ESRI's Experience Builder web mapping platform (<https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/4d5e366ea7b34c41a9670977e99df20f/>). The application has not undergone thorough peer review, widespread use, or tests for completeness and usability. As such, it merely represents a case study and prototyping exercise in support of the Salmon Expert Panel, drawing from the data and information needs identified at the 2024 workshop.

Figure 3. Screenshot of the UTEP/Nuna Technologies salmon web mapping application prototype.

More than 13,000 observing sites related to salmon, and more than 30 other biophysical, infrastructure (e.g., fish ladders), and jurisdictional data layers from multiple Alaska state and U.S. federal agencies are accessible through point-and-click menu choices. Users can explore historical fish count data, daily salmon escapement records, and real-time stream gauges, as well as information on fish passage barriers, freshwater fish inventories, and critical hydrological features. The application is expandable and highly customizable but at present does not include many of the most innovative web mapping visualization and analytical tools and usability considerations.

To further illustrate pertinent features of web mapping applications and the lessons learned from the team's development of mapping applications since the early 2000s, a number of other portals and webmapping applications were discussed in terms of their relevant features and considerations for development/sustainability (listed in [Appendix I](#)).

Designing a Portfolio of Salmon Knowledge Applications

The presentations and discussions highlighted the need for more than one salmon information portal. Instead, a set of multiple knowledge applications was envisioned as best meeting the needs for a variety of use cases and users. Many strong examples of salmon applications already exist, such as the Alaska Fish Counts app and the Pacific Salmon Explorer. However, each comes with their own gaps in coverage, reinforcing the need for additional purpose-built tools. To identify such potential tools, participants organized themselves into four groups, each envisioning a “killer app” framed around a primary audience facing a unique challenge. Each group articulated key features and functionalities for their app.

A Research-Centric “Salmon Connect” Application

The first group envisioned a central research discovery and connection hub aimed primarily towards academic and agency researchers. The emphasis on this application is on linking datasets to researchers, institutions, funders, publications, and observing assets to

improve transparency, collaboration, and cross-institutional discovery. Key features and functionality included 1) raw data access, data submission and synthesized views; 2) contextual linking that allows navigation across relationships, for example datasets to researchers, or publications to observing assets; 3) comparative analysis of related variables across multiple data sources; and 4) language translation to broaden accessibility.

An In-Season Fishery and Hatchery Management Application

This app was proposed as an operational decision-support tool emphasizing timely integration and interpretation of monitoring data to improve coordination and management outcomes for use by agency managers, hatchery operators with secondary relevance to commercial, subsistence, sports fishers, and local communities. Key features included 1) automated integration of thermal mark, fish ticket, and escapement data; 2) generation of standardized fishery performance metrics; 3) spatial and temporal analysis of run timing and movement patterns; and 4) archiving and comparison of in-season data with verified historical records to reduce conflicting interpretations.

Incentivizing High-Quality Salmon Data Contribution and Reuse

This proposed app was framed as a data stewardship and incentive platform aimed at addressing persistent gaps in data submission, documentation, and reuse for data collectors, data managers, and community data contributors. Its key features included 1) guided dataset submission to appropriate repositories; 2) metadata enrichment and quality assessment; 3) reputation and reward systems based on data contribution and reuse; and 4) social networking features such as user profiles, badges, and dataset feedback to promote sustained engagement and accountability.

A Community-Centered Watershed Adaptation and Restoration Application.

This proposed app is a dynamic, multi-scale decision-support environment to support understanding of environmental change and inform adaptive action. The intended

audience is local and Indigenous communities, subsistence users, regional and federal agencies, Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMO) participants, NGOs, and other watershed stakeholders, spanning individual users to large institutions. Its key features include 1) integrated synthesis of environmental, biological, and monitoring data; 2) summary indicators of watershed and salmon system health; 3) climate threat assessment and scenario exploration; and 4) user-specific views and profiles that enable different interaction modes for situational awareness, contextual understanding, and planning. The app also emphasized transparency regarding data sources, governance, and links between observations, decisions, and outcomes.

Participants converged on a shared conclusion: the concept of a single, all purpose “salmon portal” is neither realistic nor desirable. Instead the session articulated a vision for a portfolio of interconnected applications, each designed around specific use-cases, audiences, decision contexts and incentives, but grounded in shared data infrastructure, standards, and governance.

Together, these visions reinforce that no single application can effectively address all salmon data needs, but each application benefits from being part of a broader, coordinated ecosystem. A “portal” is less a standalone destination and more an entry point to a broader set of applications/tools that have a shared data infrastructure, standards, and data models, that support salmon research, management, and stewardship activities.

Portal Design and Features

Despite differences in audience and scope of the demonstration portals and design session, several common design principles and elements emerged consistently, and fall into the following categories:

Design Principles

- Applications must be explicit about their primary users and decision-context, with a *user-first design*, rather than attempting to generalize across all possible audiences.
- Use cases should drive portal feature development and scope.
- Trust depends on *transparency* and *traceability* into data sources, coverage, limitations, and *how* data are linked to interpretations and decisions.
- Shared data standards and knowledge models must be the foundation of the various applications.
- Trends in web mapping application development at the interface of environment, policy, and stakeholder engagement suggest the need for innovative design. Specifically, there is a growing demand for tools that integrate disparate and complex data in a user-friendly way, without constraining users to fixed workflows. Instead, the design should provide AI-integration and user-defined visualization, analytical, and output capacities.

Inclusivity and Community

- Effective systems must accommodate locally held or Indigenous data.
- Portals should include different methods of communicating data. Story maps are an especially effective tool for sharing data in an accessible format.
- Portals should be designed to support data and knowledge from Tribal organizations and Indigenous communities, with features that include videos, audio, and testimonials while preserving context and sovereignty.
- Portals should have the ability to navigate linkages/relationships across datasets, people, institutions, and decisions over fully harmonizing all data into a single integrated product.

Technical Capabilities and Infrastructure

- Web mapping applications offer a capacity to provide users with access to disparate and large data and information sources, a range of data types, discovery and visualization tools, analytical capabilities, and output products. They are also easier than ever to technically design, develop, and maintain.
- Access to standardized, high quality, and machine readable data is arguably one of the most development-limiting, cost effective, and sustainability-limiting components of any web mapping application development effort.
- There have been several exciting horizon-expanding web mapping technological and other developments and innovations (e.g., AI, data interoperability, analytics) in recent years that are directly relevant and could greatly enhance efforts associated with a salmon portal development.
- The embedding of AI agents in web mapping applications showcased is a developmental frontier and early results suggest a transformative potential for growth, innovation, and effectiveness.

Development and Sustainability

- Challenges for the creation and upkeep of a portal may be more social than technical, with the need to incentivize data contribution and the coordination with existing efforts and governments.
- Stakeholders and users will always have shifting and growing needs, capacities, interests and motivations. These often go beyond initial design specifications and are fueled by new capacities realized through use of prototype and newly released applications. An agile software development strategy is thus highly recommended as a means for ensuring co-production and iteratively meeting dynamic stakeholder and user needs, as well as for communicating such dynamics and expectations to project personnel, funding agencies, contributors, and others.

- It is important to develop applications from the outset with a pragmatic mindset and knowledge of capacities and anticipated constraints for sustainability and scalability respectively.
- Outreach, education, and training should be an essential component of any application development, launch, and sustainability plan. The best applications can fail miserably if they are not advertised effectively and users do not become familiar with the application and its capacities.

Knowledge Modeling

This session was led by the [Research Data Alliance Salmon Ontology Working Group](#) (RDA SOWG), who are engaged in building a shared salmon knowledge framework for enabling interoperable salmon data, knowledge integration, and decision support. Brett Johnson from Department of Fisheries and Oceans, Canada led the session and emphasized how nuanced and inconsistently used terms such as “*wild salmon*”, “*escapement*”, or “*stock*” or “*compound assessment metrics*”, create barriers to data-sharing and integration. Workshop participants were introduced to ontologies as formal infrastructure for making context explicit and machine-readable and a

useful backbone for enhancing capacities for synthesis across distributed salmon data systems. The session emphasized that ontologies are not about replacing local or Indigenous Knowledge systems, but about creating *translation layers* that allow diverse terminologies and contexts to coexist while remaining interoperable. The session presented the roadmap adopted by SOWG, showing how organizational ontologies (e.g.,

DFO, SASAP) can align under a shared Salmon Domain Ontology while preserving sovereignty and local control.

The discussion indicated strong community alignment around the need for shared semantic infrastructure to support salmon knowledge sharing. Some of the key takeaways:

- Participants identified several salmon-related terms whose meanings vary or are ambiguous, making cross-dataset comparisons difficult. Frequently cited terms were *escapement* (and its many goal-based variants), *return*, *run*, *wild*, *stock*, *population*, *habitat*, *catch vs. harvest*, *productivity*, *systems* and *resilience*. Measurement-related terms (e.g., length, size, age) were also highlighted as problematic due to differing methods, units, and aggregation practices.
- Discussion emphasized that differences in meaning are not simply technical but contextual, shaped by perspectives, cultural frameworks, and lived experience. For example, the term *value* is different for fishermen, scientists, and subsistence fishers. Participants stressed that resolving ambiguity must preserve this contextual richness.
- Participants expressed strong support to value knowledge from Indigenous communities and non-native English speakers and that ontologies may serve as an effective medium for sharing knowledge across the contextual boundary of western science and traditional ecological knowledge.
- Participants emphasized that ontologies must be designed not as abstract artifacts, but as practical translation layers that could help answer questions such as: *Am I measuring the same thing you are? What assumptions are embedded in this metric? How can data collected using different methods be meaningfully compared?* The ability to clearly present methods, units, spatial definitions, temporal scope, funding context, and uncertainty was seen as essential for building trust and enabling synthesis

- Community participation is important; members' questions, terms, and use cases must directly inform ontology design, reinforcing a co-production model for salmon knowledge infrastructure.

Salmon Data Access

Throughout the workshop, there was a recurring notion that salmon data mobilization is not purely a technical challenge, but a sociotechnical undertaking that includes considerations related to governance, equity, and long-term stewardship barriers. Lack of shared metadata standards, naming conventions and common

terminology, differences in formats, documentation practices, and definitions make it challenging to reuse or synthesize data even when it is nominally open. Participants noted that data can be difficult to locate, publication is often delayed relative to the need for timely action and decision-making, and critical contextual information such as sampling conditions, methodological limitations, or operational constraints is frequently lost. Without this context, it is often not clear how data should be interpreted; for instance, whether reported values (e.g., counts, returns) reflect true measures or are influenced by methodological or logistical factors.

Participants also highlighted that institutional and legal concerns further limit data sharing. Agencies expressed hesitancy to release data due to uncertainties around reuse, liability, and the potential for misinterpretation when datasets are used outside their original context. Inadequate metadata and missing provenance information increase the risk that data may be misapplied in decision-making, regulatory processes, or public discourse, leading to reputational or legal consequences. These concerns reinforce that

improving data access is not simply a matter of openness, but of responsible data stewardship.

The discussion underscored the need for a Salmon Knowledge Portal that supports both centralized discovery and federated, or standardized, access. Participants emphasized that such a portal must be grounded in shared metadata standards and common language, including collaboratively developed vocabularies. Community-driven efforts, such as the Research Data Alliance Salmon Ontology Working Group, were highlighted as promising pathways for co-developing vocabulary and semantic standards in partnership with data producers, data stewards, and domain knowledge experts, rather than imposing top-down frameworks.

These conversations were explicitly framed around the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable; [Wilkinson et al., 2016](#)) data principles with particular emphasis on interoperability and reusability. However, participants stressed that FAIR alone is insufficient in salmon context. There was strong implied emphasis on CARE principles (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics; [Carroll 2020](#)),

specifically defined to guide Indigenous data and knowledge governance. Ensuring Indigenous data sovereignty, equitable access, and ethical reuse requires clear governance structures, explicit guidance on appropriate use of data, and mechanisms to prevent misuse or interpretation outside of cultural and ecological context.

Participants further emphasized that inclusion must extend beyond access to data. Involving Indigenous communities, subsistence users, scientists, managers, and policymakers in the co-production of the design of data portals, and infrastructures was identified as essential for building trust, ensuring relevance, and making participants feel seen and heard. Special attention is needed for handling sensitive information and uncertainty.

Finally, the workshop highlighted the importance of long-term sustainability and maintenance. Participants cautioned that without sustained funding, governance, and stewardship, data portals become one-time projects that will quickly become obsolete.

6. Synthesis, Funding Opportunities, and Collaboration

The workshop identified a high degree of connectivity of information needs, research questions, and knowledge portal concepts across different sectors with ties to Pacific salmon. The pilot portals explored in the demonstration session, along with the synthesis of underlying datasets, highlighted the need for a concerted effort to advance development and implementation of information and knowledge-sharing infrastructure. Much of the value of such a knowledge portal lies in the creation of a framework that connects salmon data, information, and knowledge across scales from freshwater spawning-ground redds to oceanic gyres. International collaboration can both furnish a multitude of resources and guide prioritization of support by identifying a set of observables (e.g., based on SAON ROADS Salmon Expert Panel guidance) that addresses

pressing questions around present state and future trajectories of Pacific salmon populations. Harmonization and centralization of salmon information products and data may also help state agencies to operate more efficiently and benefit in a more direct fashion from advances in research and data management. Funding to initiate and advance such a concerted effort would need to be obtained through different channels, ranging from national programs, e.g., programs supported by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) or the North Pacific Research Board, to international efforts such as under the auspices of private foundations, or bi- or multilateral funding agreements such as the Belmont Forum.

The thematic breakout session arrived at these key conclusions and follow-on activities:

- Meeting participants seek to continue collaboration, including through in-person meetings such as the Salmon Connections Conference in Vancouver in 2026 or the Arctic Science Summit Week in 2026, with a need to identify collaborative frameworks supporting development of joint proposals for funding support, coordinated observing campaigns and - most importantly - development of a knowledge portal that spans the breadth of these activities.
- Collaborative frameworks: Connect to organizations such as the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and its working groups, in particular those with cross-cutting themes; the Research Data Alliance (RDA, <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/>) might also serve as host of virtual convening spaces, though with caveats about the much greater breadth of RDA as a whole; a newly established Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ArORA) may help in connecting with the wider ocean observing community; the Pacific Salmon Foundation and Atlantic Salmon Trust may serve a similar function for salmon-focused research.
- Funding approaches: US NSF programs, both Arctic-specific and cross-cutting, hold promise to acquire funding for design and implementation of initial information infrastructure, pilot observing campaigns, and a first iteration of an operational

knowledge portal. The pressing need for up-to-date inventories of observing assets, as highlighted in the section above on Counting Assets & Portal Use Cases, would provide further motivation to fund such a request. Advancing one or two of the “killer app” ideas that align with these goals may help build further momentum and bring in other funding partners.

- Policy and decision-making relevance: The Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC) and its collaboration teams are both audience or users of a salmon knowledge portal in the context of federal resource management, as well as funders for aspects that meet agency information needs. Working closely with IARPC, including on salmon data initiatives, will ensure policy relevance and fundability of proposed work on a knowledge portal. At the international level, the current priority to strengthen U.S.-Japan cooperation bodes well for work on a portal and a series of associated shared data products for Japan, the U.S., and Canada. The North Pacific Anadromous Fish Commission (NPAFC) has needs for data integration across North Pacific related to stock assessments, which may help further motivate integration across international agencies.

7. Acknowledgements

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant Nos. 1936805, 1936556, 1936626, 1936579, and 2042102, and the Sasakawa Peace Foundation. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation or the Sasakawa Peace Foundation. We would like to thank Nicole Greco for her help with formatting this document.

8. References

- Alaska Department of Fish and Game (ADF&G). (2026). AYKDBMS, (Arctic-Yukon-Kuskokwim Database Management System). Retrieved 30 April 2026 from https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/CF_R3/external/sites/aykdbms_website/Default.aspx.
- Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., et al. *The CARE Principles for indigenous data governance. Data Sci J* 2020; 19: 43.
- DataONE. (n.d.). *State of Alaska's Salmon and People (SASAP) portal*. Data Observation Network for Earth. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from <https://search.dataone.org/portals/SASAP>.
- Diack, G., Bull, C., Akenhead, S. A., Van Der Stap, T., Johnson, B. T., Rivot, E., et al. (2022). Enhancing data mobilisation through a centralised data repository for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.): Providing the resources to promote an ecosystem-based management framework. *Ecological Informatics*, 70, 101746.
- Diack, G., Bird, T., Akenhead, S., Bayer, J., Brophy, D., Bull, C., et al.. (2024). Salmon Data Mobilization. *North Pacific Anadromous Fish Commission Bulletin*, (7), 61-76.
- Donkersloot, R., Black, J. C., Carothers, C., Ringer, D., Justin, W., Clay, P. M., et al.. (2020). Assessing the sustainability and equity of Alaska salmon fisheries through a well-being framework. *Economy and Society*, 25(2).
- Feddern, M.L., Schoen, E.R., Shaftel, R., Cunningham, C.J., Chythlook, C., Connors, B.M., Murdoch, A.D., von Biela, V.R., and Woods, B. (2023). Kings of the north: Bridging disciplines to understand the effects of changing climate on Chinook Salmon in the Arctic–Yukon–Kuskokwim region. *Fisheries* 48(8): 331–343. doi:10.1002/fsh.10923.
- Feddern, M.L., Shaftel, R., Schoen, E.R., Cunningham, C.J., Connors, B.M., Staton, B.A., von Finster, A., Liller, Z., von Biela, V.R., and Howard, K.G. (2024). Body size and early marine conditions drive changes in Chinook salmon productivity across northern latitude ecosystems. *Global Change Biology* 30(10): e17508. doi:10.1111/gcb.17508.
- Klope, M., Jones, M., Dann, T., Diack, G., Eicken, H., Lekanoff, R., Lescak, E., Manley, W., Rand, P., Vogel, J., & Wayner, H. (2024). Equitable Information Portal Design for Mobilizing Salmon Knowledge. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.18739/A2H70827T>
- Krupa, M. B., Cunfer, M. M., Clark, S. J., & O'Dean, E. (2018). Resurrecting the public record: assessing stakeholder participation in Alaska's fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 96, 36-43.

Oke, K. B., Cunningham, C. J., Westley, P. A. H., Baskett, M. L., Carlson, S. M., Clark, J., et al. (2020). Recent declines in salmon body size impact ecosystems and fisheries. *Nature communications*, 11(1), 4155.

Rand, P. S., & Ruggerone, G. T. (2024). Biennial patterns in Alaskan sockeye salmon ocean growth are associated with pink salmon abundance in the Gulf of Alaska and the Bering Sea. *ICES Journal of Marine Science*, 81(4), 701-709.

Shaftel, R., Feddern, M.L., McAfee, S.A., Schoen, E.R., Cunningham, C., von Biela, V.R., Paul, J., Cheng, Y., Newman, A., Perdue, M., Schwenk, J., von Finster, A., and Falke, J. (2026). Integrating climate data and river modeling to reveal Chinook salmon habitat conditions in subarctic river basins. *Ecosphere* 17(1): e70399. doi:10.1002/ecs2.70399.

University of Alaska Fairbanks. (n.d.). *Research Networking Activities for Coordinated Observations (RNA CoObs)*. Google Sites. Retrieved February 3, 2026, from <https://sites.google.com/alaska.edu/rna-observations/>

Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*, 3(1), 1-9.

Appendix I: Portals and Resources

Portal Name	Link
<i>Presented Salmon Information Portal Examples</i>	
Chinook Salmon Data for the Arctic-Yukon-Kuskokwim Region	https://wvo52l-megan0feddern.shinyapps.io/AYKChinook/
DataOne Salmon Portal	https://search.dataone.org/portals/9121354
UTEP / Nuna Technologies Portal	https://experience.arcgis.com/experience/4d5e366ea7b34c41a9670977e99df20f/
<i>Additional Salmon Information Portals</i>	
Alaska Department of Fish & Game Fish Count Data Search	https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/sf/FishCounts/
Alaska Department of Fish & Game GIS Data Downloads	https://www.adfg.alaska.gov/index.cfm?adfg=maps.data
Alaska Fish Counts App	https://alaskafishcounts.com/
Fisheries Oceans Canada Open Government Portal	https://search.open.canada.ca/opendata/?owner_org=dfo-mpo
International Year of the Salmon	https://yearofthesalmon.org/
North Pacific Anadromous Fish Commission	https://data.npafc.org/dataset
NuSeds-New Salmon Escapement Database System	https://open.canada.ca/data/en/dataset/c48669a3-045b-400d-b730-48aafe8c5ee6
Pacific Salmon Explorer	https://www.salmonexplorer.ca/
SalHub: Salmon Ecosystem Data Hub	https://shiny.missingsalmonalliance.org/SalHub/
State of Alaska People and Salmon	https://alaskasalmonandpeople.org/
Upper Columbia Salmon Recovery Board	https://www.ucsrb.org/data-portal/

Data Portal	
<i>Other Geospatial Data Portal Examples</i>	
Alaska Lands Viewer	https://arctic.utep.edu/Alaska-Land-Management-Viewer/
Arctic Observing Viewer	https://arcticobservingviewer.org/
Arctic Research Cruise Viewer	https://arctic.utep.edu/Research_Cruise_Viewer/
Arctic Research Mapping Application	https://armap.org/
Barrow Area Information Database (BAID)	https://barrowmapped.org/

Appendix II: Participants

The Workshop included over 50 in-person and virtual participants from the academic, consulting, government, Indigenous, and non-profit groups (Figure S1). Participants joined from the United States, Canada, Japan, and the United Kingdom (Figure S2).

Figure S1. Workshop Participants by Sector

Virtual Meeting Participants

Participant Affiliations

Irene D. Alabia

*Arctic Research Center
Hokkaido University*

Tom Bird

Fisheries and Oceans Canada

Courtney Carothers

University of Alaska Fairbanks

Curry Cunningham

University of Alaska Fairbanks

Tyler Dann

Alaska Department of Fish and Game

Monica Diaz

Pacific States Marine Fisheries Commission

Hajo Eicken

*International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks*

Tav Ammu

*Alaska Sea Grant
University of Alaska Fairbanks*

Hekia Bodwitch

University of Alaska Southeast

Bruno Carturan

Pacific Salmon Foundation

Casey Cusick

Ahtna Intertribal Resource Commission

Graeme Diack

*Missing Salmon Alliance
Atlantic Salmon Trust*

Kelly Drummond

*Skipper Science Partnership
Aleut Community of St. Paul Island*

Lara Erikson

Pacific States Marine Fisheries Commission

Thomas Farrugia

Alaska Ocean Observing System

Sue Grant

Fisheries and Oceans Canada

Jordan Head

Bristol Bay Science & Research Institute

Mary Hostetter

*Tribal Steward
Igiugig Village Council*

Brett Johnson

Fisheries and Oceans Canada

Brandi Kamermans

*International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks*

Delores Larson

United Tribes of Bristol Bay

Bert Lewis

Alaska Department of Fish and Game

Andrew Magel

Kuskokwim River Inter-Tribal Fish Commission

Bronwyn McDonald

Fisheries and Oceans Canada

Andrew Munro

Alaska Department of Fish and Game

Allison Gaylord

Nuna Technologies

Koh Hasegawa

*Salmon Research Department
Japan Fisheries Research & Education Agency*

Adelheid Herrmann

*Alaska Center for Climate Assessment and
Preparedness/ International Arctic Research
Center/ University of Alaska Fairbanks*

Yuki Iino

*Salmon Research Department
Japan Fisheries Research & Education Agency*

Matthew B. Jones

*National Center for Ecological Analysis and
Synthesis
University of California Santa Barbara*

Maggie Klope

*National Center for Ecological Analysis and
Synthesis
University of California Santa Barbara*

Emily Lescak

*International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks*

Jeff Libby

*Applied Environmental Research Center
University of Alaska Anchorage*

William Manley

*Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research
University of Colorado Boulder*

Mel Morrison

Fisheries and Oceans Canada

An Nguyen

*Oden Institute for Computational Engineering and
Sciences, University of Texas at Austin*

Jamie O'Connor
Intertidal Consulting
International Arctic Research Center - Salmon
Expert Panel Facilitator

Ava Peters
Dartmouth College

Mark Saunders
NPAFC International Year of the Salmon (retired)

Toby Schwoerer
International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Jim Simon
Yukon River Inter-Tribal Fish Commission
Ahtna Intertribal Resource Commission

Kelsey Stanbro
Ahtna Intertribal Resource Commission

Shirly Stephen
National Center for Ecological Analysis and
Synthesis
University of California Santa Barbara

Nels Ure
Commercial Fishermen for Bristol Bay

Harmony Wayner
Western Alaska Landscape Initiative- Northern
Latitudes Partnerships/ Alaska Conservation
Foundation
International Arctic Research Center - Salmon
Expert Panel Facilitator

Gottfried Pestal
SOLV Consulting

Pete Rand
Prince William Sound Science Center

Erik Schoen
International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Tommy Sheridan
Alaska Blue Economy Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Kurt Solander
Environmental Science Division
Los Alamos National Laboratory

William Stanbury
North Pacific Anadromous Fish Commission

Craig Tweedie
University of Texas at El Paso

Chris Waigl
International Arctic Research Center
University of Alaska Fairbanks

Appendix III: Workshop Agenda

November 12, 2025: Introduction & review of previous efforts

8:30 AM - 4:30 PM

- 9:00 - 10:00 Session 1: Welcome + Introductions
- 10:00 - 10:30 Break
- 10:30 - 11:30 Session 2. Project Introduction and Background
- 1:00 - 2:15 Session 3: Lightning Talks 1
- 2:15-2:30 Break
- 2:30-3:15 Session 4: Lightning Talks 2
- 3:15-4:15 Session 5: Survey of Existing Portals
- 4:15-4:30 Wrapup

November 13, 2025: Demo portals

8:30 AM - 4:30 PM

- 9:00-9:30 Session 6: Welcome + Icebreaker
- 9:30-10:30 Session 7: Portal Demo 1 - Counting Assets
- 10:30-11:00 Break
- 11:00-12:00 Session 8: Portal Demo 2 - DataOne
- 1:30-2:30 Session 9: Portal Demo 3 - UTEP
- 2:30-2:45 Break
- 2:45-3:45 Session 10: General discussion and recommendations about portal designs, data needs, and functionality
- 3:45-4:30 Wrap-up & Group Photo

November 14, 2025: Next steps

8:30 AM - 3:00 PM

- 9:00-9:15 Session 11: Welcome
- 9:15-10:15 Session 12: Research Data Alliance Salmon Ontology Working Group
- 10:15-10:30 Break
- 10:30-11:30 Session 13: Roadmap for design, development, and sustainability
- 1:00-2:30 Session 14: Thematic breakouts for ontology WG, deliverables, portals, virtual
- 2:30 - 3:00 Session 15: Final discussion, review next steps, and requested participant actions

Appendix IV: Lightning Talks

Presenter	Title
Brett Johnson	Practical Data Stewardship for Salmon Biologists
Gottfried Pestal and Scott Akenhead	From Salmon Data to Salmon Knowledge
Tom Bird	A Salmon Knowledge Portal in the Age of Large Language Models
Graeme Diack	RDA Salmon Research and Monitoring Interest Group
Bruno Carturan	Pacific Salmon Foundation and the Pacific Salmon Explorer
Sue Grant and Bronwyn MacDonald	What is the State of Canadian Pacific Salmon
Thomas Farrugia	Alaska Ocean Observing System (AOOS) Overview and Ocean Data Explorer
Hekia Bodwitch	Engaging Indigenous Knowledge in Policy Making: Fisheries Management in Alaska
Kelly Drummond	Skipper Science Partnership
Yuki Iino and Koh Hasegawa	Salmon Fisheries & Research In Japan
Toby Schwoerer	Applied Economic Research Using SASAP Data
An Nguyen	Inverse Modeling: Potential Applications for Salmon Marine Stressors Studies
Tommy Sheridan	Mariculture Workforce Development at ABEC
Pete Rand	Copper River Salmon Data Synthesis/Modeling
Irene D. Alabia	Marine Habitat Shifts of Chum Salmon at Sea
Courtney Carouthers	Untitled
Mary Hostetter	Drone surveys of Nanvarpak tributaries
Curry J. Cunningham	Alaska, Coast-wide and High Seas Salmon Synthesis

References for Graphics and Photos

Title Page

Salmon graphic from Canva, created by Vectortradition

Page 2

Wave graphic from Canva, created by Nurfajri Aldi

Page 4

Salmon in river from Canva, courtesy of IPGGutenbergUKLtd from Getty Images

Page 6

Salmon pattern graphic from Canva, created by Yulia Zelinskaya

Salmon jumping photo from Canva, by Supercaliphotolistic from Getty Images

Page 13

Salmon graphic from Canva, created by heyrabbiticons

Page 25

Salmon missile photo from Canva, by Supercaliphotolistic from Getty Images

Page 26

Alaska buildings photo from Canva, by Carmengabriela from Getty Images

Page 28

Salmon photo from Canva, by dsafanda from Getty Images